

NODES – Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile

FLAGSHIP PROJECT GRIP

SPOKE 2 –GREEN TECHNOLOGIES AND SUSTAINABLE INDUSTRIES

DELIVERABLE D7.3: Extracts and pure compounds suitable for pharmaceutical, nutraceutical, cosmetic applications and DELIVERABLE D7.4: Extracts suitable as biopesticides

REPORTING PERIOD	
Period covered:	from M1 to M26
Periodic report date and version:	30/06/2025
Deliverable D7.3 Responsible	Stefano Superchi (Unibas)
RM7 Responsible	Stefano Superchi

This report is part of the project NODES which has received funding from the MUR – M4C2 1.5 of PNRR funded by the European Union - NextGenerationEU (Grant agreement no. ECS00000036)

Glossary

	Definition
Hub Coordinator (HC)	The Hub Coordinator represents the single point of contact for the implementation of the innovation ecosystem towards the MUR. It carries out the management and coordination activities of the innovation ecosystem, receives the fundings, verifies, and transmits to the MUR the reporting of the activities carried out by the Spoke and their affiliates.
National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP)	This document uses the Italian acronym for the NRRP, which is PNRR (Piano Nazionale della Ripresa e Resilienza)
Research Program Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the NODES project. The NODES will appoint the Research Program Manager. It refers to "Responsabile del Programma di Ricerca" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
NODES' Research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spoke, with the aim to promote and support applied research on topics consistent with the Intelligent Specialization Strategy, with the guidelines of the 2021-2027 partnership agreement scheme, with regional operational plans and regional and national research and innovation priorities. Although NODES' Spokes are concentrated on different themes, they will organize their activities and actions within a common framework – NODES' Booster Methodology
Spoke Coordinator	The University in charge of coordinating the Spoke's ecosystem. It refers to "Spoke" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
Spoke Data Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the monitoring and management of data generated at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Data Manager.
Spoke Partner	The entity associated to the Spoke Coordinator. It can be an Innovation Cluster, Competence Center, Research Center related to the Spoke's ecosystem and contributes to achieve objectives and impact under the Spoke' leadership and management. It refers to "soggetti affiliati" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione".
Spoke Project manager	The person who will be the responsible for the management, coordination and progress of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Project Manager.
Spoke research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spokes. The spoke will leverage a consolidated collaboration with leading private and public companies and will focus the applied research activity on technological domains and applications that can favour the integration of SMEs into new value chains.
Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager.
Spoke Stakeholders Committee (SC)	Consultation structure formed by relevant stakeholders (Government, universities, companies, civil society, third sector, etc.)
Spoke Thematic	General target focus and domain of the Spoke research.
Spoke Topics	Specific areas/lines of development within the Spoke.
Spoke Work Package Leader	At the Spoke level, Work Packages (WPs) will be organized by WP leaders, who will be responsible for performance evaluation and reporting.
Flagship Project	Main research project at the Spoke level with the goal of prototyping, testing, demonstrating the research activities towards higher TRLs.

Table 1 - List of Deliverables

NUM	OUTPUTS/DELIVERABLE NAME	TYPE*	SHORT DESCRIPTION	LEAD PARTICIPANT	DISSEMINATION LEVEL **	DUE DATE
D7.1	Data on type, quality, availability, and geographical distribution of agro-forest waste and by-products	R	Report and a database on distribution and availability of biomass suitable for valorization	UNIBAS	PU	M12
D7.2	Delivery of validated extraction protocols according to the treated biomass type	R	Report on validated methodologies for value-added extracts depending on biomass type	UNIBAS	PU	M22
D7.3	Extracts and pure compounds suitable for pharmaceutical, nutraceutical, cosmetic applications	Other (material)		UNIBAS	PU	M26
D7.4	Extracts suitable as biopesticides	Other (material)		UNIBAS	PU	M26
D7.5	Report on bio-chemical characterization of biomass extracts and pure compounds	R		UNIBAS	PU	M28
D7.6	Biomaterials for bioactive extracts delivery	Other (material)		UNIBAS	PU	M26
D7.8	Formulates for pharmaceutical, nutraceutical, cosmetic applications (in collaboration with companies)	Other (material)		UNIBAS	PU	M28
D7.9	Formulates for agro-chemical applications (in collaboration with companies)	Other (material)		UNIBAS	PU	M28
D7.10	Protocol for scale-up production of valuable bioactive mixtures and compounds from agro-forest waste and by-products	R	Report on validated methodologies suitable for scale-up and industrial production	UNIBAS	PU	M30

Table 2 - List of Project Milestones

MILESTONE NUMBER	MILESTONE NAME	RELATED WORK MODULES	DUE DATE (MONTH)	MEANS OF VERIFICATION
M7.1	Survey on regional scale of the type, quality, availability, distribution of biomass from agro-forest waste	7	8	Report
M7.2	Selection of biomass materials suitable for valorization (at least three)	7	10	Report
M7.3	Validation of extraction protocols for selected matrices and materials	7	12	Report
M7.4	Availability of biomass extracts (at least five) suitable for bio-activity tests	7	16	Material
M7.5	Production of a report on bioactivity of different materials and compounds	7	20	Report
M7.6	Availability of biomaterials for bioactive material delivery	7	26	Material
M7.8	Availability of formulates for pharmaceutical, nutraceutical, cosmetic applications	7	28	Material
M7.9	Availability of formulates for agro-chemical applications	7	28	Material
M7.10	Protocol for scale-up production of valuable bioactive mixtures and compounds from agro-forest waste and by-products	7	30	Report

INTRODUCTION

The final target of the Research Module 7 activity is the valorization of waste and by-products from the agro-forest industry of Basilicata through the production of valuable chemicals and intermediates for pharmaceutical, nutraceutical, cosmetic, agriculture applications. To achieve this target, in the Deliverable 7.1 a data collection on agro-forest waste and by-products production of Basilicata has been carried out and the most promising waste for valorization have been selected. The selection has been carried out taking into account the waste availability, the environmental problems connected to their disposal, and the potential for valorization depending on the valuable metabolites content. In Deliverable 7.2 the optimized procedures for extraction of bioactive metabolites from grape pomace and pomegranate waste were reported. In this Deliverable 7.3 selected biomasses are studied for valorization by means of extraction of valuable bioactive metabolites. The bioactive metabolites content of the extracts from grape pomace and pomegranate waste obtained through different methodologies has been ascertained in order to establish the most promising for employment suitable for pharmaceutical, nutraceutical, cosmetic applications. **As the presence of polyphenols and flavonoids can make the products suitable for both medical and agricultural purposes as biopesticides, in this report we joined results related to both Deliverable 7.3 and Deliverable 7.4.**

1. Selected biomass extracts

1.1 Extract from grape pomace waste.

Our studies on the extraction methods on grape pomace waste provided a deep insight into the most relevant pros and cons of the commonest extraction modes. The analysis of the antioxidant properties of the extracts allowed to identify accelerated solvent extraction (ASE) and digestion (DIG) as the most promising ones. Such test made it possible to identify the hydroalcoholic extracts obtained by using ASE and microwave (MW) as the most active extracts. However, although these extraction techniques are environmentally sustainable, their large-scale industrial application is often complex. Therefore, digestion (DIG) at 60°C for 2 hours was chosen as the selected extraction protocol. This conventional extraction method has proven to be economical and suitable for large-scale production, especially for small companies. The grape pomace extract obtained by this method was characterized and employed for further biological activity studies (*vide infra*). The characterization of the DIG extract selected for further biological studies is reported below.

Phytochemical analysis: *In vitro* spectrophotometric assays

An important quality factor for red wines is represented by polyphenols, which are highly related to wine sensory descriptors like structures, astringency, and bitterness. Amidst the by-products produced during winemaking, the pomace retains high total polyphenol content depending on the grape variety or winemaking techniques. A great deal has been devoted to developing analytical methods for determining grape polyphenolic composition with a view to planning interventions, from selecting the harvest date to controlling winemaking and wine aging processes. However, only a few investigations were performed on evaluating Aglianico Grape pomaces, and no extraction methods have been defined. Hence, the effect of two different extraction techniques, DIG (as a conventional extractive method) and ASE (as an unconventional extractive technique), coupled with hydroalcoholic solvent, were compared based on the recovery of tannins, flavonoids, and anthocyanins from different Aglianico grape pomace (Table 1).

Table 1. Phytochemical analysis

SAMPLE	TFC	AN	TTC	HT	CT
	mgQE/g	mgMA/g	mgTAE/g	mgTAE/g	mgCE/g
B ASE	555.38 ±40.18 ^b	13.38 ±0.57 ^c	2253.62 ±112.28 ^{a,b,c}	971.16 ±73.23 ^{a,b,c}	238.86 ±14.73 ^a
T ASE	709.02 ±53.31 ^a	13.09 ±0.75 ^c	2209.71 ±127.55 ^{a,b,c}	780.3 ±72.56 ^c	220.33 ±7.46 ^{a,b}
CNS ASE	405.88 ±30.63 ^c	14.04 ±0.92 ^{b,c}	2140.93 ±206.23 ^{b,c}	999.21 ±52.66 ^{a,b}	212.45 ±15.14 ^{a,b}
B DIG	801.34 ±54.18 ^a	17.08 ±0.76 ^a	2676.37 ±223.86 ^a	843.43 ±79.02 ^{b,c}	133.46 ±10.35 ^d
T DIG	810.81 ±51.61 ^a	15.71 ±1.00 ^{a,b}	1912.53 ±128.95 ^c	1005.15 ±37.08 ^{a,b}	188.62 ±17.3 ^{b,c}
CNS DIG	437.01 ±35.75 ^{b,c}	14.66 ±0.70 ^{b,c}	2548.48 ±227.03 ^{a,b}	1136.05 ±107.34 ^a	152.34 ±13.22 ^{c,d}

DIG, digestion; ASE, accelerated solvent extraction. Aglianico Grape of Torre- cuso (T), Barile (B), and Cantine del Notaio (CNS); TFC, total flavonoid content; AN, anthocyanins; TTC, total tannins content; HT, hydrolyzable tannins; CT, condensed tannins. The results are reported as mean ± standard deviation; different letters (a-d) indicate statistically significant differences ($p < 0.05$)

Tannins

The name Tannin is generally used to describe a polyphenolic nature complex biomolecule that has a sufficient number of hydroxyl and other groups, such as carboxyls, to form stable complexes with a wide variety of macromolecules. Tannins are secondary plant phenolic compounds commonly grouped into hydrolyzable and condensed tannins. In the context of the present investigation, the content of total tannins in Aglianico grapes pomaces varied between 1912.53 ± 128.95 and 2676.37 ± 223.86 mgTAE/g. Hydroalcoholic DIG and ASE methods yield similar amounts of tannin, indicating that both extraction techniques are effective for obtaining these specialized metabolites.

Flavonoids and anthocyanins

Nearly 6000 flavonoid molecules have been reported in plants, classifying flavonoids as a significant family of secondary metabolites representing 13–30 % of the total phenolic content of red grapes. The most abundant flavonoids to be found in the grape are anthocyanins, which are present only in red pomace. In the present investigation, the amount of flavonoids varied from 405.88 ± 30.63 to 810.81 ± 51.61 mgQE/g, while that of anthocyanins ranged between 13.09 ± 0.75 and 17.08 ± 0.76 mgMA/g. The greatest quantity of anthocyanins was achieved in Torrecuso and Barile grape pomace varieties subjected to hydroalcoholic DIG, obtaining high values (from 5.3 ± 1.7 to 10.3 ± 1.4 mgMA/g). However, these differences may be related to berry ripening as a close correlation has been found between anthocyanin biosynthesis and the degree of berry ripeness. The highest levels of extracted flavonoids were achieved at high temperatures (60–90 °C).

In conclusion, using five eco-friendly extraction methods (MAC, DIG, MW, US, ASE), it was demonstrated that the choice of extraction technique significantly influences the bioactivity of the recovered compounds. Our results demonstrated that DIG emerged as the most effective technique, particularly for Barile grape pomace extracts. These findings suggest that DIG could be a cost-effective and industrially scalable method for producing high-value bioactive extracts. The major strength of this work lies in its integrative approach, combining eco-friendly extraction methods with advanced analytical techniques such as HRMS/MS and molecular networking. This latter allowed detailed metabolic profiling of Aglianico pomace extracts, identifying known and unknown compounds with promising antioxidant and chemopreventive properties. Additionally, the study highlights the potential of these extracts for their application in nutraceutical and pharmaceutical fields, contributing to the valorization of agro-industrial by-products.

The DIG extracts of different grape pomace origin were then chosen for the subsequent biological evaluation studies and for pharmaceutical and nutraceutical applications.

a) Extraction methods of bioactive compounds from pomegranate waste.

Aim of the study was the comparison of different extraction methods of pomegranate waste taking into account their efficacy (in terms of yield of recovered total extract), its selectivity towards different classes of metabolites, its economy and scalability, its environmental impact and sustainability. In particular, traditional water/ethanol extraction was compared with innovative and *green* methods, such as deep eutectic solvents (DES), dimethylcarbonate (DMC), and 2-MeTHF solvent. Different extracts were obtained from pomegranate (*Punica granatum* L.) waste coming from juice production. The samples were obtained from “Azienda Agricola Mercorella” di Scanzano Jonico (MT). Subsequently, the ethanolic extract and the different parts of pomegranate (pericarp, mesocarp, seeds) were separately extracted with different DES to obtain fraction enriched in bioactive compounds. In fact, DES solvents are generally considered

as non-toxic and environmentally friendly solvents. Moreover, DES solvents extracts could be used as they are in cosmetic preparations, without isolation of the bioactive components. Many different DES were then prepared by mixing Choline Chloride/Glycerol, oxalic acid, Urea, Levulinic acid, lactic acid, ethylene glycol, camphor/menthol (hydrophobic DES) in different molar ratios (Table 2).

Table 2. Hydrogen bond acceptors (HBA) and donors (HBD) employed for DES preparation.

Name	Component 1 (HBA)	Component 2 (HBD)	Component 3 (HBD)	Molar ratio
DES 1	ChCl	Glicerol	//	1:2
DES 2	ChCl	Glicerol	//	1:3
DES 5	ChCl	Urea	//	1:2
DES 9	ChCl	Lactic acid	//	1:1
DES 12	Camphor	Menthol	//	1:1,7
DES 15	ChCl	Levulinic acid	Urea	1:1:1

In addition to DES, other low environmental impact solvents already known for the extraction of bioactive compounds such as 2-MeTHF and DMC were used. Moreover, 2,2,5-trimethyl-1,3-dioxolan-4-one, supplied by the Isuschem company, has been also employed for the first time for extractions of bioactive compounds. The metabolites content in the extracts was then determined by LC MS/MS spectrometry. A preliminary investigation was first carried out using only DES 1, DES 1 back-extracted with 2-MeTHF, neat 2-MeTHF, DMC, and ethanol (Table 3 and 4). All extracts are concentrated to dryness, except DES 1 for which this operation is not possible.

Table 3. Flavonoids content on total residue extract.

Flavonoids (mg/g)	EST37 (EtOH) (mg/g)	EST38 DES 1 (mg/g)	EST38-R back-extracted DES 1 (mg/g)	EST39 (MeTHF) (mg/g)	EST40 (DMC) (mg/g)
Kaempferol	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	0.11±0.01
Miricetin	n.d.	n.d.	0.19±0.01	0.19±0.01	0.19±0.01
Baicalein	0.04±0.005	0.04±0.01	0.05±0.01	0.04±0.01	0.04±0.02
(-)-Epigallocatechine gallate hydrate	0.19±0.005	0.15±0.005	0.20±0.005	0.40±0.01	0.33±0.005
(+/-)-Naringenin	n.d.	n.d.	0.01±0.005	0.02±0.005	0.02±0.005
Baicalin	0.01±0.005	0.01±0.005	0.01±0.005	0.02±0.005	0.016±0.002

Apigenin	0.04±0.005	0.03±0.005	0.04±0.005	0.04±0.005	0.06±0.001
Rutin hydrate	0.02±0.005	0.01±0.005	0.12±0.005	0.06±0.005	0.004±0.001
Phlorizin	0.05±0.005	0.04±0.003	0.11±0.003	0.16±0.01	0.38±0.02
Hesperetin	n.d.	n.d.	0.02±0.001	0.02±0.001	0.03±0.001
Naringin dihydrochalcone	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.12±0.003

Table 4. Polyphenolic acids content in total residue extracts.

Polyphenolic acids (mg/g)	EST37 (EtOH)	EST38 DES 1	EST38-R back-extracted DES 1	EST39 (2-MeTHF)	EST40 (DMC)
4-hydroxybenzoic acid	nd	nd	<LOQ	0.002±0.0006	0.01±0.001
Ellagic acid dihydrate	1.18±0.03	0.40±0.004	1.89±0.03	3.85±0.08	5.34±0.06
Gallic acid	0.08±0.004	0.05±0.005	0.4±0.007	0.86±0.003	1.24±0.04
3,5-Dihydroxy benzoic acid	nd	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.0015±0.001

Kaempferol was found at relatively interesting concentrations exclusively in the DMC extract (0.11 mg/g); the content of myricetin is instead identical in the DES 1 back-extracted with 2-MeTHF, in the 2-MeTHF extract and in the DMC extract (0.19 mg/g), while it is not present in the ethanol extracts and in the DES 1 extracts; the content of baicalein, epigallocatechin gallate, naringenin, baicalin and apigenin is similar between the various extracts, the only substantial difference concerns the content of epigallocatechin gallate in the 2-MeTHF extract (0.4 mg/g), slightly higher than in the other extracts. The content of rutin hydrate is higher in the back-extracted DES (0.12 mg/g), while it is lower in the DMC (0.004 mg/g). The content of phlorizin in the DMC extract is 8 times higher than that of the ethanol extract (0.38 vs 0.05 mg/g) and is 2 times higher than that of the 2-MeTHF extract (0.38 vs 0.16 mg/g) while naringin dihydrochalcone is present only in the DMC extract. The most important data concerns ellagic acid dihydrate, clearly higher in the DMC extract (5.34 mg/g), but still quite high also in the 2-MeTHF extract (3.85 mg/g), compared to the ethanol, DES and DES back-extracted extracts (1.18 mg/g, 0.40 mg/g and 1.89 mg/g). The same trend occurs for gallic acid: the amount of gallic acid in the DMC extract is 15 times higher than that in ethanol and is 40% compared to that in 2-MeTHF.

Among the various solvents compared, the most promising is DMC, followed by 2-MeTHF, while the least efficient solvents are ethanol, DES 1, and DES 1 back-extracted. In any case, the back-extracted DES still appears to have an interesting profile, which highlights the effectiveness of the back-extraction method.

Table 5. Bioactive compound extractions in different solvents and DES

Solvent	(-)-Epigallocatechin gallate hydrate (mg/g)	(+/-)-Naringenin (mg/g)	Phloridzin (mg/g)	trans-Cinnamic acid (mg/g)
DES 1	n.d.	0.020±0.0002	0.034±0.005	3.842±0.131
DES 2	n.d.	0.021±0.002	0.026±0.004	3.855±0.642
DES 5	0.129±0.001	0.019±0.0003	0.040±0.019	3.790±0.081
DES 9	0.129±0.001	0.021±0.0003	0.043±0.009	4.166±0.476
DES 15	n.d.	0.021±0.001	n.d.	3.412±0.188
DES 12	0.128±0.0002	0.021±0.002	0.036±0.001	3.671±0.189
DES 12 + DES 1	n.d.	0.0218±0.002	n.d.	4.125±0.383
EtOH	0.129±0.0003	0.022±0.001	n.d.	3.328±0.075
EtOH/H ₂ O	0.128±0.0001	0.022±0.0007	0.026±0.007	4.017±0.648

Notably, results obtained by LC-MS/MS show how the DES, show extraction efficiency comparable to ethanol and the ethanol/water mixture and, in some cases, even higher.

Table 6. Bioactive compound extractions in different solvents and DES.

Solvent	(-)-Epigallocatechin gallate hydrate (mg/g)	(+/-)-Naringenin (mg/g)	Phlorizin (mg/g)	trans-Cinnamic acid (mg/g)
EtOH	0.129±0.0003	0.022±0.001	n.d.	3.328±0.075
EtOH/H ₂ O	0.128±0.0001	0.022±0.0007	0.026±0.007	4.017±0.648
DIOX	n.d.	0.020±0.0002	0.028±0.012	3.985±0.004
2-MeTHF	n.d.	0.020±0.001	n.d.	4.024±0.137
DMC	n.d.	0.021±0.001	0.019±0.009	3.500±0.187

As inferred from Table 6, the other low environmental impact solvents used also extracted bioactive compounds in quantities comparable to the classical solvents.

The DMC extract demonstrates the best profile, a particularly interesting finding, given the apparent lack of publications on pomegranate waste extraction using this *green* solvent. One of the problems to overcome for *in vitro* biological assays with DES extracts is the solvent toxicity towards cells cultures. This excludes the direct use of the extract in DES and makes the use of

the back extraction technique with more compatible solvents like 2-MeTHF and DMC mandatory. Therefore, to perform the biological assays and for pharmaceutical and nutraceutical applications as well as the test as biopesticides, the ethanol, the 2-MeTHF and the DMC extracts were chosen.

CONCLUSION

As far as the grape pomace extraction is concerned, different eco-friendly extraction methods (MAC, DIG, MW, US, ASE) were employed, demonstrating that the choice of extraction technique significantly influences the bioactivity of the recovered compounds. Our results demonstrated that DIG emerged as the most effective technique suggesting that DIG could be a cost-effective and industrially scalable method for producing high-value bioactive extracts.

Therefore, **DIG extracts from grape pomace were further evaluated for their biological properties and chosen for pharmaceutical and nutraceutical applications.**

Pomegranate waste was instead treated with either traditional water/ethanol extraction or innovative and *green* methods, such as deep eutectic solvents (DES), dimethylcarbonate (DMC), and 2-MeTHF solvent. The DMC extract was undoubtedly the most promising, followed closely by the 2-MeTHF extract, and the ethanol extract.

Therefore, **to perform the biological assays and for pharmaceutical and nutraceutical applications the ethanol, as well as the tests as biopesticides the 2-MeTHF and the DMC extracts were chosen.**